

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE ACTIVITY OF THE AZERBAIJAN CREATIVE UNIONS IN THE FIELD OF PROPAGANDA IN THE 60 – 80s OF THE XXth CENTURY IN THE SCIENTIFIC WORK OF PROFESSOR NISBET MEHDIYEVA

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ABSTRACT

Azerbaijan has always been known all over the world for its outstanding representatives, invaluable intellectuals, scientific and cultural figures, educators and scientists who have made the great contributions to the development of education and science, talented researchers who have worked extensively and effectively in various fields of science, personalities who have risen to the highest peaks of science, and eternally young and eternal sons and daughters. These individuals have been specially selected for their intense and tireless activity in the continuous development of Azerbaijan science and have always been distinguished by their uniqueness. One of the prominent intellectuals of Azerbaijan historical science, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor and outstanding historian Nisbet Mehdiyeva, has courageously stepped into very difficult fields of science and conducted major researches. In the research works dedicated to the creative work done and carried out by Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva in the field of activity and propaganda of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions, the activity of these organizations in the development of culture in our country in the 1960 – 1980s, the exposure of talented and creative individuals, the promotion of the scientific potential of each individual, the improvement of the general cultural level of the people and the population, the creation of a business and creative environment for talented and truly capable individuals engaged in creative activities, the involvement of the country's prominent intellectuals in this creative process, the formation of a sound and correct policy of the state in the field of cultural development and other topical issues were extensively studied and found their worthy scientific solution as a result of the great efforts of the scientist. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's intense, highly creative and productive scientific activity in this field is undeniable. The researches conducted by Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva in the field of the activity of Creative Unions engaged in artistic creation in the formation of the general cultural level of society, also its basing on the national – moral values of Azerbaijan and the most perfect scientific and cultural examples of the world, should be considered the great creative success.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Creative Unions, propaganda, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, scientific creativity, historical science, intellectual, activity.

Introduction

One of the characteristic features of the modern era is that it includes decisive means and ways to shape, encourage, develop, direct and promote the activity of people in the political, economic and cultural spheres, and to develop and implement the necessary action plans for this purpose. Thus, the development of all these areas is directly connected in the developing and promotion of culture. From this point of view, the complex development of culture means the gradual maturation, development and formation of areas directly or indirectly related to it. The state's concern for the development of professional and amateur creativity, despite the difference between the professional creativity, distinguished by its uniqueness, has its own path, has mastered all its subtleties in this field, and has become the more prepared cadre over time, and amateur creativity, which is still opening new paths and trying to speak its mind, it is quite remarkable that both are given a place in the society, promoted and encouraged. The activities carried out by the Creative Unions in the field of promoting works of art take an important part in this work [4, 3].

The activity of the Creative Unions in the field of propaganda

When it comes to propaganda, organizational measures, forms and methods of writing works, mass propaganda, its organization and other theoretical and practical aspects should be taken into account. The establishment of propaganda bureaus and department is envisaged as organizational measures. The activity of propaganda bureaus includes the organizing meetings of creative intellectuals with people, organizing readers' and audience conferences, holding debates and other mass cultural events, organizing the activity of people of various creative professions in the field of propaganda, developing a work plan with people of different age categories, building a moral bridge between creative intellectuals and readers and audiences, forming the ideological, moral and aesthetic education of society and other theoretical and practical measures.

Through the propaganda bureaus, the series of important events, such as the regular meetings, events, round tables, disputes, discussions, debates and etc. have been held between the creative intellectuals and readers and viewers in the country. In this context, the creation of new works, the development of creative forms and methods, the holding of discussions of beautiful examples of art and works that are the products of the artistic imagination of creative intellectuals, the

identification of creative searches and etc. can be considered as the main directions of propaganda. At the same time, the main spheres of propaganda are reading lectures, participating in the work of cultural universities, regularly holding poetry days and weeks, providing patronage for the organization of cultural events and the activity of the creative organizations, organizing the practical work with cultural and educational institutions, caring for the development of artistic creativity, showing exhibitions, promoting music, organizing the festivals on a regular basis, promoting theater performances, cinema – propaganda, discussing and showing films, taking scenarios from real life events and basing them on real facts, making feature and documentary films, etc. In 1973 alone, the Union of Artists of Azerbaijan and the Ministry of Culture of Azerbaijan jointly organized 100 exhibitions [16]. However, it should also be noted that, along with these literary and artistic works that reflect serious social and moral problems, real facts, important issues, and episodes arising from the real life of the country and people, it is also possible to come across works that are banal, weak, and written and created to please someone. At the same

time, demonstrating the principle position in the activity of the creative unions, responsibility, demandingness, care for talent, preventing their destruction and elimination by all means, both by the state, citizens and creative organizations, should be considered one of the most important and necessary tasks facing the country's creative intellectual environment. From this point of view, in the creation of all literary and artistic works and various examples of art, characteristics such as honesty, humanity, humanism, art and science, and responsibility towards the country have been guided, and the citizen, creative intellectual has always approached the events taking place in the country, the current socio – political situation, the state of the country, and the negative situations and shortcomings we encounter in our daily lives from this prism, from the citizen's perspective, and has always gone his own way and tried to have his say. In this regard, the extensive research works conducted in this field by the historian, great educator, and lifelong intellectual, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva [Image 1], as well as the current issues she raises and the beautiful research works that always resonate with reality and defend the supremacy of truth and justice, are quite remarkable.

Image 1. Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's textbook "The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of mass propaganda (1960 – 1980s)" [4], her book "The cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions (1960 – 1980s)" [5], her monograph "The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of the development of culture (1960 – 1980s)" [3] and other works are quite noteworthy in this regard and should be considered the fundamental research works in studying the activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions.

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's textbook "The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of mass propaganda (1960 – 1980s)" [Image 2] is dedicated to the mass propaganda activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of widely distributing the works of literature and art using the various forms and methods. The events, exhibitions, festivals, screening of theater and cinema works and other important points carried out by the creative intellectuals in the field of promotion of artistic culture are covered in detail.

Image 2. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's textbook "The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of mass propaganda (1960 – 1980s)" (1990)

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's book "The cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions (1960 – 1980s)" [Image 3] reflects the activity of the Azerbaijan Writers' Union in the republic in the field of literary translation, promotion of literature, relations in the field of literary and cultural events and other important creative aspects. The book examines and explains in detail the multidisciplinary relations between the Unions of Composers, Artists, Cinematographers, the Theater Society and the "Azerbaijanfilm" studio through the works of music, painting, theater and cinema. The book also highlights the aspects such as the mutual implementation of these relations with relevant unions and

organizations in the country and abroad. In addition, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva put forward the certain proposals in the book to improve the forms and methods of cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions, increase their efficiency and made the number of recommendations to eliminate shortcomings occurred during the creative process. The valuable scientific work and extensive activity carried out by the researcher in this field can be considered the product of the great scientific researches of the valuable scientist, based on real facts and practical activity.

Image 3. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's book "The cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions (1960 – 1980s)" (1991)

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva's monograph "The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of the development of culture (1960 – 1980s)" [Image 4] reflects the issue of the activity of the Writers' Union, Composers' Union, Artists' Union, Theater Workers' Union and Cinematographers' Union in the field of the development of culture in Azerbaijan historiography. The author has extensively researched the ideological and political level of creative intellectuals in the country, their professional skills, the creative and organizational work of unions, their role in the promotion of artistic culture and their activity in the field of cultural relations. This research work by Professor Nisbet

Mehdiyeva is of great interest. The activity of the Creative Unions is very diverse, significant and unique, and reflects the various cultural issues. These creative organizations, engaged in purely creative and artistic activity, take an important part in raising the cultural level of the people. The researcher, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, in addition to dedicating space to the achievements and successes gained in the process of explaining and investigating each issue, also noted the shortcomings and mistakes made, indicating the need to develop an important practical action plan to eliminate them.

Image 4. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva and her monograph "The activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of the development of culture (1960 – 1980s)" (2014)

In our country, the part of the Creative Unions in the implementation, organization and formation of cultural education work and other spheres is unique. In the effective implementation of this activity of the Creative Unions, the role of the Propaganda Bureau and Club, Exhibition Hall, Art Gallery, Composers' House, Cinema House, Actors' House, etc. should be especially noted. Thus, the Bureau of Literary Promotion was established for writers, the Exhibition Hall for artists, and the Bureau for the Promotion of Music under the Union of Composers. The Exhibition Hall, established in 1960, was transformed into the Azerbaijan State Art Gallery in 1974 [4, 6; 2].

The department promoting the cinematography began operating under the Azerbaijan Cinematography Workers' Union in 1962. This department regularly held wide – ranging lectures, creative meetings and various events [13].

In the promotion of literary and artistic works, it is necessary to specially mention the part and activity of the organs of the Writers' Union, the newspaper "Literature and Art", the magazines "Azerbaijan", "Ulduz", "Gobustan", "Literary Azerbaijan", as well as the various press agencies of the republic [4, 10].

The television and radio, which are mass media, were also widely used in the promotion of fine arts. The twenty special programs related to the individual and

general exhibitions of artists and the dozens of short films were shown on television. The Union of Artists also actively promoted through publishing houses and periodicals. The color albums, pictures, sets of artistic postcards and etc. containing the works of Azerbaijan artists were released. The works and catalogs about the artists were also published. The artistic life of the republic, innovations in the creative environment and etc. were covered in the newspapers and magazines [10].

The cinema was also widely promoted through the television programs. Every month the television program called "Writer and screen" was organized on television. These programs discussed the current problems of screen adaptation of the literary works, the mutual relations between literature and cinema, the introduction of the best examples of literary works, the works of art that emerged as a result of the search for new plots and ideas and etc. [18, 11 – 12, 18].

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva has shown that in the 60 – 80s of the 20th century, the Creative Unions of the Republic of Azerbaijan were constantly searching for new forms in the field of increasing the educational significance of literary and artistic works. According to the researcher, one of such forms was the activity of music lectures, discussion of the works, conferences of readers and spectators, holding of the various disputes, etc. The purpose of holding these events was to establish

direct contact with a wide audience of listeners, spectators and readers, to hold creative discussions and exchange of ideas.

In 1960, the members of the Union of Artists of the Republic gave 85 lectures. These lectures were brought to the attention of readers, listeners and spectators at the events held in the various departments and organizations, military units, border regions, cultural centers, officers' houses, art museums and etc. 6.000 people attended these events [8; 12]. In 1962, the members of the Artists' Union gave 102 lectures. The geographical map of the lectures organized each year was quite extensive [4, 23].

The Bureau of Fiction Promotion of the Writers' Union in the republic organized 27.563 meetings of writers in 1970 – 1975. For about 200 writers participated in these meetings. Most of these meetings were devoted to individual reports, lectures, disputes, discussions, creative reports, discussion and analysis of new creative forms and methods, meetings and events in the form of questions and answers with readers, round tables, various interviews, evaluation of creative activity and determination of directions, etc. [4, 24]. The researcher drew the special attention to these issues and emphasized their importance.

In the 70s of the 20th century, the Azerbaijan Theater Society, guided by the theme of effective use of the lecture – propaganda tool, organized 596 lectures on the problems of theater art in the various cities of the republic in just 6 years. The topics of these lectures were “Realism in Theater”, “Modern Reading of Classics”, “Actor in the Puppet Theater”, etc. Thus, the lectures on these topics were aimed at familiarizing the audience with the problems of theatrical art, theater repertoires and artistry issues, the problem of the actor and the stage in 20th century theater, modern theater through the eyes of the audience, aspects of theater and realism, the formation of theatrical vision, the place of theater in modern life, the establishment of the concept of actor and audience, the reflection of real – life facts and events in theater, etc. issues were aimed at solving, analyzing and realistically staging them [14].

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva notes that the Propaganda Bureau of the Union of Cinematographers of Azerbaijan organized 440 lectures on the promotion of cinematography almost every year [19, 10]. According to the researcher, these lectures organized by the Creative Unions of the Republic were delivered by literary critics, theater critics, art critics, music critics and film critics. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva also indicated that the art critics and critics working and specializing in the relevant arts were also involved in this work [4, 25].

These various forms of propaganda, each functioning in its own unique way, played the decisive role in the cultural and aesthetic education and formation of the taste of the population.

The poetry days, painting days, literature and art weeks, which were regularly held by the Creative Unions, also played the important role in the promotion of works of art. The poems read at the poetry days held annually by the Writers' Union were later published in the separate books [4, 30].

On the Artist's Day, held by the Union of Artists of the Republic from April 1 to 16, 1961, 8 exhibitions

were opened, 4 reports were read, 10 talks were organized, and 15 meetings were held. In this regard, 7 radio and 9 television programs were prepared and broadcast, and articles were published in the newspapers. In this series, “Artist's Day” was also held in the cities of Baku, Sumgayit, Ganja and Neft Dashlar, where the professional artists, art historians, critics and other creative intellectuals participated [9].

The literary and cultural relations

The Azerbaijan Creative Unions were closely involved in the international relations. According to the researcher, the forms and means of these relations are rich, the scope is wide, the geography is boundless and the importance is great. At the meetings held in the Creative Unions, international cultural relations, translation problems, discussions, disputes, interviews, the role and place of international relations in the formation and development of the creative environment, various creative issues and problems and other aspects were given wide space [5, 5].

The prominent researcher notes that the forms and methods of relations between the Azerbaijan Creative Unions and institutions and organizations engaged in the publication, exhibition and promotion of literary and artistic works of various countries are quite diverse. The acquaintance, learning, establishing contacts, exchange, development and other forms and methods occupied the important place in the activity of these organizations [5, 7].

The work done to study the international cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions, the collected materials and facts are diverse and valuable. Thus, their writing, analysis and formulation are extremely necessary. The international relations of the Creative Unions mainly covered the issues of literary – cultural relations and cooperation in the field of art.

The mutual influence and enrichment in the field of cultural relations is one of the important issues and is always highlighted by its relevance. The mutual national enrichment and cultural cooperation play the important role in establishing and strengthening international relations. The cultural heritage of peoples and their progress in this field are also manifested through the cultural relations.

The main activity of the Azerbaijan Writers' Union in the field of international cultural relations was literary translation and promotion of literature. The researcher considers that this is why the Union had the translation department [3, 199]. The translation and publication of a number of works into Azerbaijanian language, and examples of Azerbaijan literature into the various languages of the world, as well as the publication of translations of prose, poetry and drama in literary publications, could be considered one of the most important issues facing the Writer's Union [3, 200, 201]. In the 60s and 70s of the XXth century, the works of more than 100 Azerbaijan artists – a total of about 500 books – were translated into the languages of Russian, Ukrainian, Belarusian, Georgian, Latvian, Estonian and other peoples [3, 206].

The literary and cultural relations of the Azerbaijan Writers' Union included the cooperation with Poland, Bulgaria, Hungary, Italy, Spain, England, France,

USA, Mongolia, Vietnam, Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq and other countries of the world [3, 200 – 215].

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva shows in her research that during this period, Azerbaijan – European literary relations were on a large scale. The relevant institutes of the Azerbaijan Academy of Sciences and departments of higher education institutions studied and disseminated these relations, and the separate collections were published [3, 215 – 216].

In the 70s and 80s of the XXth century, the “Ganjlik” publishing house began to publish the most valuable pearls from the treasury of world literature – valuable works in 50 volumes in an elegant layout. Although most of these works were known to the Azerbaijan reader, this series was for the first time that they were published as a whole, as a system. The pearls from the treasury of World Literature were published regularly until 1990 [3, 216].

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva notes that in the development of cultural relations, along with the translated literature, book publishing and book promotion, the mutual exchanges in the field of holding book months and book fairs were of great importance.

In 1975, the republic participated in the International Book Exhibition – Fair under the motto “Azerbaijan at the International Book Fair”. The International Book Exhibition – Fair held in 1977 was attended by the various foreign publishing houses, book trade companies, enterprises and organizations specializing in the publishing equipment and printing, etc. [3, 218].

In the 80s of the XXth century, the German Foreign Trade Association “Buxexport” held the wholesale book fair in Baku [3, 219].

In the 70s of the XXth century, Azerbaijan Culture Days were held in Bulgaria, Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Poland and Denmark, and Culture Days of these countries were held in Azerbaijan [3, 227].

In 1986, at the VIII Congress of Azerbaijan Writers, the issues such as the renewal of the methods of activity of the creative unions and organizations, and cultural centers, the enrichment of the content of their activity, the meeting of the requirements of the time of all works written, translated and performed in the languages of other peoples, the organization, publication, distribution and promotion of translation work were of a major nature and were examined in detail in the researcher’s works and the attitude to the issue was expressed from the prism of the socio – political analysis of the time [3, 229].

The cooperation in the field of art

The inexhaustible wealth of every nation, along with its language and history, is also its music. Taking care of Azerbaijan music that has been passed down through the centuries, developing, modernizing, promoting and distributing it are the most important tasks facing the Union of Composers of Azerbaijan. For the wide dissemination and promotion of the musical works, art festivals, song and dance festivals, harvest festivals, the release of albums and discs, performances by artists, festivals and other forms and methods were used. According to the researcher, the activity of Azerbaijan composers and musicologists in the field of song promotion were aimed at a wide audience of viewers and listeners [4, 66]. In this regard, an example can be

given of the “Arts Festival” held at the Republic Stadium in 1961. More than 60 thousand spectators attended this event [17].

Along with the educational, cultural and scientific centers, the creative unions also actively participate in the formation of the artistic and aesthetic taste of the population, the constant enrichment of its spiritual and moral values, the instilling of a sense of beauty in people so that they can mature as harmoniously developed personalities, and the understanding and appreciation of the unique beauty of works of art, historical and architectural monuments. The researcher notes that in the 1960s, the transcribed works of Azerbaijan composers were widely promoted and sold. In 1965, a store opened in Baku selling new musical works, where music lovers could purchase scores of composers’ works [6; 7]. In the field of music promotion in the country, the possibilities of radio and television programs were used. One of the events that the creative unions participated in and organized in the field of promotion of works of art was festivals. In this regard, the researcher noted the music festivals, film festivals, theater and drama festivals, amateur creativity festivals, etc. events. In 1974, the Republican Song Festival was held [20]. The 1976 art festival featured the works by composers from Western Europe, Azerbaijan and other republics [4, 73]. The Azerbaijan composers and musicologists actively participated in the VII International Music Congress in 1971, the III International Music Tribune of Asian and African Countries in 1973, and the International Music Symposium dedicated to the art of mugham in 1978, and performed the significant activity in the field of promotion of music [3, 236].

The film festivals were very important due to their scope and influence. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva extensively studied this sphere in her scientific work. In 1960, the scientific and technical film festival called “Science and Technology Achievements in Production” was held in Azerbaijan. During the festival, stands, exhibitions, photo showcases were organized in cinemas, 896 lectures were given, 1632 sessions were shown, and documentary films dedicated to the achievements of science and technology were demonstrated [15]. In 1986, 150 representatives from 70 film studios participated in the VII Festival of Television Youth Programs and Films in Baku [4, 75].

The researcher considers that the certain work has been done in the field of promotion of theatrical art. The cultural relations in the activity of the Azerbaijan theater developed systematically. In the 60 – 80s of the XXth century, the factors such as the lack of proper regulation of the activity of actors, directors, playwrights, the development of cinema, the massification of television programs and other factors caused a certain stagnation in the development of theater.

The cultural relations of the Azerbaijan theater were carried out through the cultural events – meetings, creative relations, tours, months, decades, days, festivals, etc. The organizational measures, live contacts and various auxiliary means were used to implement such events. The various theaters, artists, writers, writer – translators, playwrights, etc. participated in the dramaturgy and theater arts festival held in Azerbaijan in 1979 [1]. At the same time, the researcher notes that the

theater days, decades and festivals of other republics were held in Azerbaijan. In 1972, the theater days of various republics were held in Baku under the organization of the Republican Theater Society [3, 261].

The creative meetings, exchanges and tours of the Azerbaijan Theater Society and the republic's theaters were very colorful [3, 263]. In 1980, the "Creative Youth Theater Week" held in Baku featured the performances based on the works by the various playwrights, as well as discussions and debates [3, 262].

The performance of works by authors from the different countries on the Azerbaijan stage, including the staging of various works by republican playwrights on the theater stages of these nations, is clear evidence of the strengthening of cultural ties between the peoples and the promotion of theater. The Azerbaijan theater groups actively participated in the Bulgarian and Hungarian drama festivals in 1968. The artists participating in the Czechoslovak Culture Decade held in Baku in 1965 performed "Tosca" and "The Legend of Love" by the Azerbaijan State Opera and Ballet Theater. These performances can be considered the main means of the cultural relations between the countries [3, 266]. In 1979, the republican artists and artistic collectives took an important part in the promotion of art in the Netherlands, the Federal Republic of Germany, Italy and Switzerland [3, 268].

The republican festivals of artistic amateurism and youth also played the certain role in the promotion of works of art. The festival of artistic amateurism held in 1970 is noteworthy in this regard [4, 78]. In 1986, the reviews, competitions and exhibitions were held at the II Republican Festival of Folk Art. Here, for the first time, the reviews of performances of drama collectives were held at the folk art festival. The professional directors, actors and theater critics watched the performances of more than 100 collectives – 48 folk theaters, 35 drama circles and 20 propaganda brigades [4, 79]. Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva rightly points out that the theater propaganda is a complex creative field. The creative organizations, theater groups, playwrights and theater critics take an important part here.

The works of art are mainly distributed and promoted through the exhibitions and reviews. The Union of Artists of Azerbaijan paid the special attention to the promotion of individual exhibitions – creative and report exhibitions. The art historians also closely participated in the promotion of works of fine art. On the one hand, the works of artists were promoted among the population through the exhibitions, and on the other hand, the presentation of art criticism works dedicated to their description and analysis to art lovers ensured the promotion of these works.

In 1960, the Union of Artists of Azerbaijan held 14 art days and 4 exhibition in the cities during the art week, which were viewed by 90 thousand spectators [12]. In 1961, more than 200 works of fine art, graphics and sculpture by 120 authors were exhibited at the republican art exhibition [11]. In 1962, 272.780 spectators viewed the exhibited works of art 97 exhibitions opened in the republic. These exhibitions were selected for their diversity [4, 57]. Between 1966 and 1970, nearly 200 traveling exhibitions were organized in the republic [4, 59].

Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva notes in her research that the exhibition creativity is the field that requires visibility, dynamism, modernity, relevance and meets the demands of the time [4, 59]. The exhibitions were considered one of the most active forms of aesthetic education of people. Along with the exhibitions of paintings organized by the Union of Artists, viewing of sculptures, drawing, designing and distributing propaganda posters could be considered the important means of promoting works of art. The Union of Artists paid the special attention to the development and promotion of the propaganda poster workshop, constantly improving its work [4, 63]. The diversity, versatility, plot variety, and unique and effective means used in the propaganda poster exhibitions organized in the republic are particularly noteworthy.

The international relations of the Union of Artists of Azerbaijan were manifested in the forms of exhibition and thematic exchanges, establishment of personal contacts, participation of representatives of the Union of Artists of different republics in the Union's events, etc. In the 70s of the 20th century, the works of Azerbaijan artists were repeatedly exhibited in different republics, and the exhibitions of art samples of other nations were extensively exhibited in the republic [3, 246].

The Azerbaijan artists had the close creative ties with the masters of brushwork from foreign countries. In 1963, the exhibition entitled "Our Contemporary" consisting of the works by Azerbaijan artists was held in Bulgaria, in 1964 the exhibitions were held in Poland and Czechoslovakia, and in 1965 two exhibitions of Azerbaijan artists were held in Prague. In 1965, 400 artists from 42 countries and 10 graphic artists from the former Soviet Union participated in the VI International Graphic Exhibition in Lyublyana. At the Lyublyana exhibition, the artist A.Rzaguliyev represented Azerbaijan with his engravings [3, 249]. In 1968 – 1970, the exhibitions were held 4 times in the German Democratic Republic, 2 times in Poland and the exhibitions in Hungary, Bulgaria and Romania. In the 70s of the 20th century, the independent exhibition of Azerbaijan artists was held in Poland, the participation of the country's artists in the Leipzig Fair in the German Democratic Republic, the exhibition of works by republican artists in Czechoslovakia, the personal exhibitions of 2 of our artists in Poland, and participation in the various events and exhibitions were ensured. The participation of republican artists in such international exhibitions has played the major role in the dissemination, promotion and development of all forms and genres of fine art [3, 249 - 250]. The exhibition "Friendship Palette" prepared with the participation of Czechoslovak artists was displayed in Baku. The Azerbaijan artists went on creative missions, painted new paintings, and were engaged in the promotion of these countries, introducing the audience to those countries and their art. In 1959 – 1960, the Azerbaijan artists were sent on missions to Czechoslovakia, Poland, Romania and Bulgaria [3, 250]. The mutual exhibition exchanges continued in the following years. The research scientist Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva shows that in 1971 – 1975, the exhibitions of works of art from Czechoslovakia,

the German Democratic Republic, Poland, Romania, etc. were held in Baku [3, 251].

Conclusion

The culture, including its components, literature and art, play the important role in the spiritual development of society. The promotion of all spheres of culture is extremely important and can be considered the most powerful means of influence in the formation of personality as an individual, an independent person. The mutual influence and enrichment in the field of cultural relations is one of the important issues and is always highlighted by its relevance. The mutual national enrichment and cultural cooperation play an important role in establishing and strengthening international relations. The cultural heritage of peoples and their progress in this field are also manifested through the cultural relations. The development and research of the field of propaganda, which is one of the main means of the cultural relations, occupies a key place in this work.

In this regard, the valuable books and monograph of the talented researcher, well – known and prominent scientist, great educator, beautiful person and mother, powerful personality, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, dedicated to the activity of the Azerbaijan Creative Unions in the field of propaganda, their cultural relations and the development of culture, are extremely valuable research works and are the very valuable source and the huge fundamental work in the study of the activity of the Creative Unions in the 60 – 80s of the 20th century. These works by Professor Nisbet Mehdiyeva, who is always young and always alive, are extremely valuable research works, just like her.

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